

Application of the Fries and Friedel-Crafts Reactions to *m*-Halogenophenyl Acetates and *m*-Halogeno-phenols

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4-Halogeno-2-hydroxyacetophenones, obtained by the Fries migration of *m*-halogenophenyl acetates, have been used for the synthesis of (a) 4-methyl-7-halogeno-coumarins by the Kostanecki acylation method, (b) 3-methyl-6-halogeno-coumarones by the Kostanecki and Tamber reaction, and (c) 3-halogeno-6-ethyl-phenols by Clemmensen's reduction.

o-Hydroxyacetophenones can be prepared from phenyl acetates by the Fries reaction or directly from the phenols by the Friedel-Crafts reaction. Various monohydric, dihydric, and trihydric phenols, naphthols, etc. have been subjected to these reactions to furnish *ortho*- or *para*-hydroxyacetophenones. Out of the *m*-halogeno-phenols, *m*-chlorophenol was studied by Tiwari¹ and 2-hydroxy-4-chloroacetophenone isolated. Chen and Chang² prepared 2-hydroxy-4-chloro- and 2-hydroxy-4-bromo-acetophenones by baking the corresponding phenyl acetates with anhydrous AlCl₃ and 2-hydroxy-4-iodo-acetophenone from *m*-iodophenyl acetate by the Fries reaction in presence of a solvent and also from aceto-*m*-anisidine. This communication deals with the preparation of 2-hydroxy-4-halogeno-acetophenones from *m*-halogenophenyl acetates by the Fries migration in presence and absence of solvent and from *m*-halogeno-phenols by the Friedel-Crafts reaction. The latter reaction failed to yield acetophenones in all the three cases. The Fries migration provided only the *ortho* isomers.

4-Halogeno-2-hydroxyacetophenones (II; R=H) were subjected to the Kostanecki acylation. The products formed were identified as 4-methyl-7-halogeno-coumarins (III) by mixed m.p. with the authentic samples of 4-methyl-7-halogeno-coumarins prepared from 4-methyl-7-amino-coumarins³. Formation of coumarins in this reaction is noteworthy because resacetophenone, under similar conditions, affords a chromone and not a coumarin⁴.

6-Halogeno-3-methylcoumarones (IV) were prepared from 4-halogeno-2-hydroxyacetophenones by the Kostanecki and Tamber reaction⁵.

[X = Cl, Br, or I; R = H, CH₂CO₂Et, CH₂COOH]

1. This Journal, 1952, 29, 41f.
2. J. Chem. Soc., 1958, 148.
3. Subbarao and Sundermury, Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci., 1956, 38A, 149.
4. Kostanecki and Rozicki, Ber., 1901, 34, 102.
5. Ber., 1900, 42, 905.

4-Halogeno-2-hydroxyacetophenones were subjected to Clemmensen's reduction, when 3-halogeno-6-ethylphenols (V) were obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (II: X=Cl; R=H).—*m*-Chlorophenyl acetate (6.8 g.) was added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (12.89 g.) in dry chlorobenzene (75 ml) and kept overnight. It was then heated on a steam bath for 4 hours, cooled, and to it ice and HCl were added. Chlorobenzene was removed by distillation which was continued further, when an oily liquid passed over. It was separated and purified, b.p. 247°. It was identical with 4-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone, prepared by a method used by Chen and Chang.²

4-Bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone (II: X = Br; R = H).—A mixture of *m*-bromophenyl acetate (7.2 g.), anhydrous aluminium chloride (15 g.), dissolved in chlorobenzene (80 ml), was treated like its chloro isomer. After removal of the solvent as above, a liquid passed over which solidified after refrigeration; m.p. 43°. This compound was found to be identical with 4-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone, prepared by a method used by Chen and Chang.²

4-Iodo-2-hydroxyacetophenone (II: X=I; R=H).—*m*-Iodophenyl acetate (10.5 g.) was cooled in a freezing mixture and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride was very slowly added to it. The temperature was then gradually raised to 120° and kept thereat for 2 hours. The reaction mass after cooling and decomposing the complex formed by ice and HCl was steam distilled, when a pink solid passed over. It was crystallised from ethanol in long, thin, colorless, shining needles, m.p. 54°, yield 6.8 g. Mixed m.p. with 4-iodo-2-hydroxyacetophenone, prepared by a method used by Chen and Chang², showed no depression.

4-Methyl-7-chlorocoumarin (III: X = Cl).—A mixture of 2-hydroxy-4-chloroacetophenone (4.5 g.), fused sodium acetate (4 g.) and acetic anhydride (25 ml) was heated at 160-70° for 6 hours. The reaction mass was poured into water and kept overnight. The resulting solid was filtered and washed with dilute NaOH solution and water. It was crystallised from 30% ethanol in shining needles, m.p. 147°, yield 1.2 g. Mixed m.p. with 4-methyl-7-chlorocoumarin, prepared from 4-methyl-7-aminocoumarin³, showed no depression.

4-Methyl-7-bromocoumarin (II: X = Br) was prepared from 2-hydroxy-4-bromoacetophenone (5.5 g.) by the Kostanecki method⁴ like its chloro isomer. The resulting product was crystallised from 30% ethanol as needles, m.p. 136°, yield 2.2 g. Mixed m.p. with 4-methyl-7-bromocoumarin, prepared from 4-methyl-7-aminocoumarin³, showed no depression.

4-Methyl-7-iodocoumarin (III: X = I).—2-Hydroxy-4-iodoacetophenone (6.5 g.) was subjected similarly to the Kostanecki acylation⁴. The solid formed was crystallised from 30% ethanol in needles, m.p. 158°, yield 25 g. Mixed m.p. with 4-methyl-7-iodocoumarin³ showed no depression.

2-(Bisoxycarbonylmethoxy)-4-chloroacetophenone (II: X = Cl; R = CH₂CO₂Et).—Dry and powdered sodium salt of 2-hydroxy-4-chloroacetophenone (4 g.) and bromoacetic ester were heated at 160-70° for 1½ hours. Excess of the ester was removed by

evaporation. The resulting solid was poured into water and then crystallised from 60% ethanol in short, stout needles, m.p. 101°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: Cl, 13.73. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 13.84%).

2-(*Carboxymethoxy*)-4-chloroacetophenone (II: X = Cl; R = CH_2COOH).—The preceding ketone (2.6 g.) was refluxed with *N*-NaOH solution (25 ml) for half an hour. The solid gradually went into solution. The solution was cooled and acidified. The resulting solid was filtered and extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution. The extract was filtered and acidified. The solid formed was crystallised from 60% ethanol, m.p. 150° (decomp.), yield 1.4 g. (Found: Cl, 15.42; equiv., 231.4. $C_{10}H_9O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 15.53%; equiv., 228.5).

3-Methyl-6-chlorocoumarone (IV: X = Cl).—The preceding compound (2 g.), fused sodium acetate (6 g.), and acetic anhydride (20 ml) were heated at 155-60° for 1½ hours and then poured over crushed ice, when a liquid separated. It was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water. On evaporation of the ether, a liquid, b.p. 218°, was obtained. (Found: Cl, 20.96. C_9H_7OCl requires Cl, 21.32%).

2-(*Ethoxycarbonylmethoxy*)-4-bromoacetophenone.—(II: X = Br; R = CH_2COOEt).—The sodium salt of 2-hydroxy-4-bromoacetophenone (5 g.) was treated with bromoacetic ester like its chloro isomer. The resulting solid was crystallised from 60% ethanol, m.p. 104°, yield 3 g. (Found: Br, 26.15. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4Br$ requires Br, 26.58%).

2-(*Carboxymethoxy*)-4-bromoacetophenone (II: X = Br; R = CH_2COOH).—The preceding compound (3 g.) was hydrolysed with *N*-NaOH (25 ml). The resulting solid after crystallisation from 60% ethanol melted at 158°, yield 2 g. (Found: Br, 28.96; equiv., 270.1. $C_{10}H_9O_4Br$ requires Br, 29.30%; equiv., 273).

3-Methyl-6-bromocoumarone (IV: X = Br).—The preceding compound (2 g.) was heated like its chloro isomer with fused sodium acetate (6 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 ml), affording a liquid, b.p. 255°, yield 0.5 g. (Found: Br, 37.58. C_9H_7OBr requires Br, 37.91%).

2-(*Ethoxycarbonylmethoxy*)-4-iodoacetophenone (II: X = I; R = CH_2COOEt).—The sodium salt of 2-hydroxy-4-iodoacetophenone (6 g.) was heated with bromoacetic ester at 160-70° for 1½ hours. The reaction mass was treated further like its chloro isomer. The solid formed was crystallised from 60% ethanol, m.p. 89°, yield 4 g. (Found: I, 36.1. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4I$ requires I, 36.5%).

2-(*Carboxymethoxy*)-4-iodoacetophenone (II: X = I; R = CH_2COOH) was obtained from the preceding compound (3.5 g.) by hydrolysis like its chloro isomer. The resulting solid after crystallisation from 60% ethanol melted at 178°. (Found: I, 39.41; equiv., 317.4. $C_{10}H_9O_4I$ requires I, 39.69%; equiv., 320).

3-Methyl-6-iodocoumarone (IV: X = I) was obtained from the preceding ketone (2 g.) like its chloro isomer, followed by similar treatments, as a liquid, b.p. 265° (decomp.). (Found: I, 48.79. C_9H_7OI requires I, 49.22%).

3-Chloro-6-ethylphenol (V: X = Cl).—To 2-hydroxy-4-chloroacetophenone (21 g.), dissolved in ethanol (100 ml), zinc amalgam (80 g.) and 70% HCl (300 ml) were added.

The whole mass was refluxed for 3 hours, cooled, decanted, and distilled to separate ethanol. The residue was extracted with ether. After removal of the ether an oily liquid was obtained. The liquid was distilled and the fraction between 232° and 235° was collected. The distillate soon solidified to a pink mass, m.p. 49°. It developed a greenish colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found: Cl, 22.60. C_8H_9OCl requires Cl, 22.69%).

3-Bromo-6-ethylphenol (V : X = Br) was prepared like its chloro isomer from 2-hydroxy-4-bromoacetophenone by the Clemmensen reduction. The resulting liquid was distilled under reduced pressure. The distillate soon solidified. The solid was crystallised from 20% ethanol, m.p. 43°. This phenol also showed a greenish colour with ferric chloride solution. (Found: Br, 30.46. C_8H_9OBr , requires Br, 30.80%).

3-Iodo-6-ethylphenol (V : X = I) was obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of 2-hydroxy-4-iodoacetophenone like its chloro isomer. The liquid formed was distilled under reduced pressure. The distillate solidified on cooling. The solid was crystallised from 20% ethanol, m.p. 62°. (Found: I, 50.84. C_8H_9OI requires I, 51.19%).

Sincere thanks of the author are due to Dr. R. C. Shah for the help received from him.

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Received January 14, 1963.